

The Impact of Management Styles on Employee Commitment

(A study of University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital)

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Abstract

This study examines the extent to which management styles relate with commitment of employees at the University of Port Harcourt teaching hospital. The population includes both employees and interns from the university teaching hospital. Autocratic and democratic styles of leadership were adopted as dimensions of leadership styles while affective and normative commitment were adopted as the measures for employee commitment. The hypotheses were tested using spearman rank order correlation and our findings reveals that a significant relationship exists between autocratic leadership and measures of commitment as well as democratic leadership and measures of commitment. The study further recommends that both styles are still relevant in today's organization and should not be neglected.

Keywords: Leadership, commitment, autocratic, democratic, normative, affective

Introduction

The advancement in health care around the world has led to most Nigerians leaving the shores of the country in search of proper care; this has led some of the citizens to their doom. Reason being, in search of health care they get into the snares of some unscrupulous elements that defraud them and/or traffic them for vital organs. If the health facilities in Nigeria were efficient there would be no need to travel abroad for medical care. This study seeks to examine one of the factors leading to the inefficiency in health care facilities in Nigeria i.e. workers' commitment and how the management styles in these facilities relate to it. Workers' commitment is a complex construct that has been defined as the relative importance between work and one's self (Loscoco, 1989). It is a person's adherence to work ethic, the commitment to career, job involvement and organizational commitment (Morrow, 1993). The success or failure of an organisation depends greatly on workers' commitment. Organizations value commitment among their employees because it is typically assumed to reduce withdrawal behaviour, such as lateness, absenteeism and turnover. Hence, there is no doubt that these values appear to have potentially serious consequences for overall organizational performance. The study of employee commitment is important because; the level to which an employee engages in his/her work, commits to it and believes in the organization's goals and purposes, desires to work and commits to specific career can greatly influence and organization's output. An organization with committed workers that are self motivated has a competitive advantage, stands a chance of increasing productivity and is at less risk of employee turnover (Vance, 2006).

Most organizations have realized that the performance of their workers plays a vital role in determining the success of the organization (Zheng, 2010; Ajila and Awonusi, 2004). As such, it is important for employers and managers alike to know how to get the best of their workers. One of the antecedent determinants of workers' performance is believed to be employee commitment (Ali, 2010; Ajila and Awonusi, 2004). As such, it is important for employers and managers alike to know how to get the best of their workers. Committed employees who are highly motivated to contribute their time and energy to the pursuit of organizational goals are increasingly acknowledged to be the primary asset available to an organization (Hunjra, 2010). They provide

the intellectual capital that, for many organizations, has become their most critical asset (Hunjra, 2010). Furthermore, employees who share a commitment to the organization and their collective well-being are more suitable to generate the social capital that facilitates organizational learning. For any organization or institution, be it public or private to thrive, the role of its human resources cannot be down played. Therefore, the continued successful existence of an organization depends largely on its workforce (Akinyemi and Ifijeh, 2013).

Commitment can be defined as the relative strength of an individual's identification with an organization and involvement in the organization. Organizational Commitment refers to the acceptance of organizational values and willingness to stay in that organization (Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001). Commitment to the organization is linked to key work related factors such as; employee absenteeism, employee turnover, employee performance and, employee citizenship behaviour (Alkhatani, 2016). Organizational commitment can be categorized into three components namely: affective commitment, continuance commitment and, normative commitment (Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001). Affective commitment is linked to the employees' emotional attachment to their identification and their involvement in the organization and is best illustrated by an employee's identification with the organization and its goals. Continuance commitment refers to the employee's assessment of whether the value cost of leaving the organization is greater than the cost of staying. Normative commitment refers to the employees feelings of responsibility to the organization.

Dale & Fox (2008) made a counter argument to the importance of leadership style for employee commitment proposing that, employees who have an intrinsic desire to perform at a high level are more welcoming of the leader's guidance, the leadership style notwithstanding, the outcome being commitment to the organization. Though this may be true, it has been established that various studies have evaluated leadership styles as antecedents of organizational commitment (Erben & Guneser, 2008). Whether the leadership style directly invokes commitment or, simply has an effect on different work situations leading to a less stressful experience, numerous studies in this area suggest that it can only be ignored to the detriment of overall organizational performance. Undoubtedly, the input of the leader contributes to the psychological contract that

the employee holds with the organization (Githuka, 2017). Avey et al. (2012) established that the psychological contract could be one that is characterized by a sense of ownership, a sense of effectiveness, accountability, a sense of duty, and a greater sense of belonging.

Avolio et al. (2004) associated commitment with three characteristics; value commitment, where one has a connection to the organizational values and goals; effort commitment, where one is willing to put in the necessary effort to achieve organizational goals; retention commitment, where one has a strong intention and willingness to continue being part of the organization. When employees are less committed, they look for other opportunities, and if those opportunities are not available, they may emotionally or mentally “withdraw” from the organisation (Lok & Crawford, 2004). Organizational Commitment is associated with the desire to remain in the organization based on rational cost-benefit considerations and a sense of moral obligation (Franke & Felfe, 2011).

It is therefore important for organizations to know the aspects that are of utmost importance and have big impact in boosting the commitment of their employees. A factor has been identified in this literature as a determinant of employee commitment. This factor is management style. However, most of the past studies on employee commitment were not related to Hospitals in Nigeria and as such may not apply to hospitals in Nigeria. Hence, the importance of examining management styles and the effects on workers’ commitment in hospitals using University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital as case study.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Research Hypotheses

H01: There is significant relationship between authoritative management style and workers' affective commitment.

H02: there is significant relationship between authoritative management style and workers' normative commitment.

H03: there is significant relationship between democratic management style and workers' affective commitment.

H04: there is significant relationship between democratic management style and workers' normative commitment.

Theoretical Framework

Contingency Theory

From the late 1950s, a new approach to organization theory was developed which became known as contingency theory. This theory argues that there is no 'one best way' to structure an

Received: 02 May 2023

Revised: 21 May 2023

Final Accepted: 02 June 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7999799>

organization. An organization will face a range of choices when determining how it should be structured, how it should be organized, how it should be managed. Successful organizations adopt structures that are an appropriate response to a number of variables, or contingencies, which influence both the needs of the organization and how it works.

These theories take a comprehensive view of people in organizations, they recommend a diagnosis of people/ task/ technology/environment – then suggest the development of appropriate solutions. Contingency theorists including Pugh, Burns and Stalker and Laurence and Lorsch have found that three contingencies are particularly important in influencing an organization's structure. These are:

- Its size
- The technology it uses
- Its operating environment.

There are two significant implications of contingency theory:

If there is no 'one best way', then even apparently quite similar organisations, for example, two nearby colleges, may choose significantly different structures and still survive and be reasonably successful in achieving their missions

If different parts of the same organisation are influenced in different ways by the contingencies bearing upon them, then it may be appropriate for them to be structured differently, for example, one university department may have a functional structure, whilst another may have a matrix structure

Theory X and Y

Douglas McGregor introduced Theory X and Theory Y in 1957 (Gannon et al., 2013). This psychological concept proposed that how one viewed human relationships to those of an enterprise determined their style of management.

Theory X proposes that people inherently lack the motivation and desire for responsibility and need to be closely supervised, directed, and tightly controlled in order to achieve team objectives (Gannon et al., 2013).

Without it, workers may become unwilling to work. This is considered the more conventional theory and results in management styles that have high degrees of control over employees.

Theory Y conversely suggests that it is human nature to be motivated by objectives and gain satisfaction through the completion of work (Chartered Management Institute, 2018).

Those who believe in Theory Y believe that it is the responsibility of management to foster environments where employees can develop potential and utilize their skills to achieve objectives (Gannon et al., 2013). This perspective leads to management styles that give the workers more decision making control and provide less supervision.

Autocratic style

Autocratic management is the most controlling of the management styles.

Variations of this style are authoritative, persuasive, and paternalistic. Autocratic managers make all of the decisions in the workplace. Communication with this type of management is one way, top-down to the employees. Employee ideas and contributions are not encouraged or considered necessary (Films on Demand, 2018). Roles and tasks are clearly defined, and workers are expected to follow these directions without question while being consistently checked and supervised (Films Media Group, 2018).

This type of style is particularly useful in organizations with hierarchical structures where management makes all of the decisions based on positioning in the hierarchy. Employees that benefit from this style of management include those who are new, unskilled, or unmotivated, as they need the supervision and clear direction. Managers can benefit greatly from using this style in times of crises or serious time constraints (Films on Demand, 2018).

The advantages of the autocratic management style are little uncertainty, clearly defined roles and expectations for employees, and the speed of decision making (Films on Demand, 2018). All decisions are made by the manager and employees are expected to be compliant leaving little room for variation or confusion. Decision-making speed is ideal and is not slowed by conflicting thought or agendas. Disadvantages include lack of staff input with ideas are not encouraged or shared. This can lead to job dissatisfaction, absenteeism, and employee turnover.

Because managers make all of the decisions, the employees is not inclined to act autonomously and may become too dependent on the manager. Not all employees want or need supervision, and as a result can become resentful and unhappy. Too many dissatisfied employees and the separation of power with an autocratic management style can lead to an 'us versus them' mentality (Films on Demand, 2018).

Democratic style

The democratic management style involves managers reaching decisions with the input of the employees but being responsible for making the final decision. There are many variations of this style of management including consultative, participative, and collaborative styles. Employee ideas and contributions are encouraged, but not necessary. Communication is both top-down and bottom-up and makes for a cohesive team.

This type of style is versatile with the advantages being more diverse perspectives involved in decision making. As employees are being taken into account before the manager makes decisions, the employees feel valued which increases motivation and productivity.

Disadvantages of the democratic management style are the time it takes to make a decision due to the gathering of ideas and opinions. There is also the potential conflict of different viewpoints playing a role in the decision making and as a result, employees can feel less valued if their input is not taken, leading to decreased morale and productivity (Films on Demand, 2018).

Affective commitment

Received: 02 May 2023

Revised: 21 May 2023

Final Accepted: 02 June 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7999799>

Affective commitment relates to how much employees want to stay at their organization. If an employee is affectively committed to their organization, it means that they want to stay at their organization. They typically identify with the organizational goals, feel that they fit into the organization and are satisfied with their work. Employees who are affectively committed feel valued, act as ambassadors for their organization and are generally great assets for organizations.

Normative commitment

Normative commitment relates to how much employees feel they should stay at their organization. Employees that are normatively committed generally feel that they should stay at their organizations. Normatively committed employees feel that leaving their organization would have disastrous consequences, and feel a sense of guilt about the possibility of leaving. Reasons for such guilt vary, but are often concerned with employees feeling that in leaving the organization they would create a void in knowledge/skills, which would subsequently increase the pressure on their colleagues. Such feelings can, and do, negatively influence the performance of employees working in organizations.

Methodology

Research Design

This is the framework or plan that guides the researcher on how to collect and analyze data (Baridam, 2001). It assists in generation of primary and secondary data and the analysis. It identifies the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. This study employs survey research design which is a systematic method of data collection that examines the relationship between the two variables. This type of research design uses questionnaires to gather information (not leaving interview and secondary data out).

Population of the Study

This represents the cluster of the elements under study; it is a set of homogenous elements within a universe that is chosen for study. In management sciences it is seen as the individual units, household or organization about which information is sought by the researcher for the study. In light of this, the population of this study consists of employees and interns of the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital which is approximately three thousand three hundred people on the average.

Sample Size Determination & Sampling Techniques

Due to the cumbersome nature of the target population, sample size determination is required to represent the entire population. It involves taking a reasonable portion of the population as a representative of the population about which generalization could be made on the basis of the findings derived from the sample. Sample size determination is the method used in selecting the sample size from the population of the study.

The Taro-Yamane's model shall be employed to determine the sample size to be used for this study.

From the formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where,

n= sample size or population not known

N= population size known

e= error limit given the population (5%)

With the total of 3300 at 95% level of confidence and error limit = 0.05

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

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$$1+N(e)^2$$

$$n = 3300$$

$$1+3300(0.05)^2$$

$$n = 3300$$

$$1+3300(0.0025)$$

$$n = 3300$$

$$1+8.25$$

$$n = 3300$$

$$9.25$$

$$n = 357$$

The sample size for this study was three hundred and fifty seven (357) which was obtained through simple random probabilistic sampling technique.

Data Analysis Techniques

The test of hypothesis was done using Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient analysis to determine the relationship between the two variables and the effect of management styles on employee commitment.

Data Analyses and Findings

H₀₁: There is significant relationship between authoritative management style and workers' affective commitment

Correlations

			AUTHOCRATIC_MANAGEMENT	AFFECTIVE_COMMITMENT
Spearman's rho	AUTHOCRATIC_MANAGEMENT	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.563**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
		N	301	301
	AFFECTIVE_COMMITMENT	Correlation Coefficient	.563**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
		N	301	301

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Our first hypothesis shows a significant relationship existing between autocratic management and affective commitment with a correlation coefficient of 0.563 and a p-value of 0.000 which is less than alpha level of 0.05; we therefore reject the stated null hypothesis. This also implies that for every outcome of affective commitment, autocratic leadership accounts for 53.6%.

H₀₂: there is significant relationship between authoritative management style and workers' normative commitment.

Correlations

			AUTHOCRATIC_MANAGEMENT	NORMATIVE_COMMITMENT
Spearman's rho	AUTHOCRATIC_MANAGEMENT	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.201**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
		N	301	301
	NORMATIVE_COMMITMENT	Correlation Coefficient	.201**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
		N	301	301

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Our second hypothesis shows a significant relationship existing between autocratic management and normative commitment with a correlation coefficient of 0.201 and a p-value of 0.000 which is less than alpha level of 0.05; we therefore reject the stated null hypothesis. This also implies that for every outcome of normative commitment, autocratic management accounts for 20.1%.

H₀₃: there is significant relationship between democratic management style and workers' affective commitment.

Correlations

			DEMOCRATIC_MANAGEMENT	AFFECTIVE_COMMITMENT
Spearman's rho	DEMOCRATIC_MANAGEMENT	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.804**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	301	301
	AFFECTIVE_COMMITMENT	Correlation Coefficient	.804**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	301	301

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Hypothesis three further shows a significant relationship existing between democratic management and affective commitment with a correlation coefficient of 0.804 and a p-value of 0.000 which is less than alpha level of 0.05. We therefore reject the stated null hypothesis. This also implies that for every outcome of affective commitment, democratic management accounts for 80.4%.

H₀₄: there is significant relationship between democratic management style and workers' normative commitment.

Correlations

			DEMOCRATIC_MANAGEMENT	NORMATIVE_COMMITMENT
Spearman's rho	DEMOCRATIC_MANAGEMENT	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.532**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	301	301
	NORMATIVE_COMMITMENT	Correlation Coefficient	.532**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	301	301

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Hypothesis four shows a significant relationship existing between democratic management and normative commitment with a correlation coefficient of 0.532 and a p-value of 0.000 which is less than alpha level of 0.05. We therefore reject the stated null hypothesis. This also implies that for every outcome of normative commitment, democratic management accounts for 53.2%.

Summary of Findings

This study has revealed that management styles account greatly for the commitment of workers in University of Port Harcourt Teaching hospital. The findings as revealed above shows that the least relationship was found within our second hypothesis which considered the relationship between autocratic management style and normative commitment and this test of hypothesis produced a coefficient of 0.201 which was the weakest as well as a p-value of 0.000, while the strongest relationship was found within our third hypothesis which considers the relationship between democratic management style and affective commitment with a coefficient of 0.953 and a p-value of 0.000.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were deduced:

- i. There is significant relationship between autocratic management style and employee affective commitment in university of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH). This means that autocratic management style significantly correlates with employee affective commitment in UPTH.
- ii. There is significant relationship between autocratic management style and employee normative commitment in university of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH). This means that autocratic management style significantly correlates with employee normative commitment in UPTH.

iii. There is significant relationship between democratic management style and employee affective commitment in university of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH). This means that democratic management style significantly correlates with employee affective commitment in UPTH.

iv. There is significant relationship between democratic management style and employee normative commitment in university of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH). This means that democratic management style significantly correlates with employee normative commitment in UPTH.

Recommendations

i. Due to the impact of autocratic management styles on affective employee commitment in UPTH, it is suggested that the hospital management does not abandon autocratic style of management entirely but adopt it as a part of its core managerial strategy.

ii. Due to the relationship between autocratic management style and normative workers' commitment, it is recommended that managers do not rely solely on autocratic management style to achieve normative workers' commitment in the hospital.

iii. From the findings, it is observed that democratic management style results in 80.4% of every outcome of affective commitment in the institution, it is hereby recommended that democratic management style be adopted as its core management practice to achieve more affectively committed employees.

iv. The findings suggest that democratic management style contributes to 53.2% of the occurrence of normative commitment; as such it is recommended that there be a blend of both management styles to achieve a stable working environment.

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Received: 02 May 2023

Revised: 21 May 2023

Final Accepted: 02 June 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7999799>

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